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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369151>**SPECIAL FEATURES OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SPREAD OF HEPATITIS B DURING ARMED CONFLICTS****Abstract.**

The consequences and scale of the viral hepatitis B epidemic, and its implications, have long been overlooked by the global medical community. Viral hepatitis has, to some extent, remained in the shadow of HIV infection, despite hepatitis B and C annually causing more deaths than HIV infection. Only in 2016 did the WHO launch the first global strategy to combat hepatitis B and C. This strategy aims to eliminate viral hepatitis as a threat to public health by 2030. However, most countries have not achieved this goal. Migrants and people affected by conflicts and civil unrest are identified as priority populations in the Global Health Sector Strategies on HIV, viral hepatitis, and sexually transmitted infections for the period 2022-2030. Furthermore, the prevalence of hepatitis B and C is highest in many low- and middle-income countries, which, combined with often inadequate healthcare infrastructure, means that the burden of disease in these countries is very high.

Armed conflicts, besides causing mass casualties among military personnel and civilians, lead to a range of problems, such as the spread of parenterally transmitted infections, including viral hepatitis B. Transmission occurs through contact with infected blood, such as during the provision of medical care without protective measures, or contact with other biological fluids. Therefore, it is important to consider the spread of infection in the context of armed conflicts to prevent a dangerous epidemic situation in the future.

Keywords: hepatitis B, armed conflict, infected blood, epidemiology.

Introduction. Hepatitis B (HBV), caused by the HBV virus, is a significant global medical and social problem. According to WHO estimates, 3.5% of the world's population (95% uncertainty interval: 2.7–5.0%), or 257 million people (199–368 million), are chronically infected with HBV; 2 billion have serological evidence of HBV infection; around 4.5 million new cases of infection are reported each year, with approximately 686,000 people dying annually from HBV infection, including from cirrhosis of the liver (CL), hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), and other adverse outcomes. Approximately 90% of children infected during the first year of life, 25–50% of children infected at ages 1–5 years, and 5–10% of people infected with HBV after age 5 will develop chronic hepatitis. Additionally, it is believed that 25% of adults infected with HBV in childhood may die prematurely from HCC or CL. The lack of effective etiotropic treatment, which would eliminate the virus from the human body in the development of chronic hepatitis, is also an undeniable problem. Currently, prevention and preventive measures are the only reliable methods to combat the spread of this infectious disease. However, during armed conflicts, when there is a high probability of injuries with bleeding wounds, the percentage of hepatitis B infection increases, as contact with infected blood is one of the main modes of transmission. Infection on the

battlefield is possible during the provision of medical care by healthcare workers or military personnel without latex gloves or during emergency blood transfusions with inadequate screening of donors for infections that can be transmitted parenterally. Among the civilian population during armed conflicts, the risk of hepatitis B also increases due to contact not only with blood but also with other biological fluids. Research on the prevalence and epidemiology of hepatitis B during war continues, as armed conflicts persist.

In a 5-year observation in Pakistan, there was noted an increase in hepatitis B incidence. A significant percentage of study subjects had HbsAg detected in their blood, indicating infection with hepatitis B virus.

In a study conducted in a conflict zone in Nigeria, positive results for hepatitis B virus were noted in 7.63% of the sampled population of 186,405 residents. The authors noted higher prevalence rates in conflict zones compared to non-conflict zones. In studies conducted among military recipients directly involved in military actions, out of 761 patients tested for hepatitis B virus, 469 individuals showed evidence of infection. Pre-transfusion indicators included anti-HBcAg at 19/1000 and chronic viral hepatitis B at 4/1000. These indicators may suggest infection directly in the combat zone.

In a study on the infectious status of hepatitis B virus in the United States military, serum samples from 10,000 service members were analyzed upon joining the armed forces and after combat operations in Iraq and Afghanistan. 110 new cases of hepatitis B virus infection related to military service, particularly associated with being in conflict zones, were identified.

Conclusion. The incidence of infectious diseases significantly increases during wartime, especially in areas experiencing active combat. The hepatitis B virus, transmitted through blood and other biological fluids, takes a leading position in such conditions. Methods for preventing infection and consequently spreading the infection include active immunization of the population and military personnel, as well as the use of personal protective equipment.

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